

The Influence of Engagement in Decision Making, Assessment of Work Environment and Achievement Motivation on Employee Job Satisfaction of Free and Free Foreign Trade of Sabang Port (BPKS) of Aceh Province, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation on job satisfaction of employees of the Free Trade Zone and Sabang Free Port of Aceh Province. The research respondents were 56 employees of the institution who were taken conveniently sampling. Data collection uses a questionnaire and then the data is analyzed by using multiple linear regression statistical equipment. This study found that involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation had a positive effect on job satisfaction of the Employees of the Free Trade and Free Trade Zone in Sabang, Aceh Province. The variable that has the greatest influence on employee job satisfaction is achievement motivation then follows the assessment in the second work environment. The results of statistical tests show that the calculated F value > F table and t count > t table, can be interpreted both simultaneously and deliberately in decision making, an assessment of the work environment of the Employees of the Sabang Free Port and Free Port Trade Zone of Aceh Province. Thus Ha's hypothesis is discriminated and otherwise the hypothesis Ho is rejected. The conclusion that can be drawn from this study is, the high and low level of job satisfaction of the employees of the Sabang Free Trade Agreement Board of Aceh Province. Significantly, it is influenced by employee involvement in decision making, their assessment of the work environment and the motivational status in the employee.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, satisfaction in Taking Satisfaction, Assessment of Work Environment, and Achievement Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important factors to be considered in managing Human Resources is the job satisfaction factor. This is because job satisfaction is very important for every employee and can have an impact on the smooth operation of the organization as a whole. If there is satisfaction in working, an employee will not be happy to carry out the work assigned to him. In turn, low job satisfaction will not only lead to a

lack of employee morale, but more extreme can lead to intention among employees to look for other organizations that can provide better job satisfaction. Conversely, employees feel satisfaction in working; will tend to work better for the agency where he works. Job satisfaction of employees as members of the organization can have a large influence on the results of work / performance. ^[1] With job satisfaction, an employee will try to stay within the

organization and work hard to achieve the goals of the organization itself.

Furthermore, achievement motivation is essentially a strong desire to achieve success in work characterized by efforts to self-actualization, concern for excellence and the implementation of optimal tasks based on rational. Employees will tend to be motivated to carry out work if the job can fulfill what is desired in connection with the implementation of the work. The weak strength of achievement motivation depends on the amount of hope that is to be achieved, the strength of the basis that gives rise to motivation and the amount of satisfaction desired. Special characteristics of people who have a high need to participate are happy to assume responsibility and are confident in their abilities. ^[2]

The business entity of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Zone (BPKS) is one of the institutions whose existence is greatly needed in the effort to exploit the Sabang Free and Free Port Area. The existence of this institution was stipulated through Law No. 37 of 2000 concerning the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Area. Through the Law it is stated that the Sabang area has a function as a place to develop businesses in the fields of trade, services, industry, mining and energy, transportation, maritime affairs and fisheries, postal and telecommunications, banking, tourism insurance and other fields. The functions as intended include two activities, namely (1) manufacturing activities, design, engineering, sorting, initial inspection, final inspection, packing and repackaging of domestic and foreign goods and raw materials, banking servants and machinery reconditioning and quality improvement and (2) the supply and development of water infrastructure and water resources, transportation infrastructure and facilities including seaports and airports, buildings and electricity networks, postal and telecommunications, as well as other infrastructure and facilities.

In carrying out its operational activities BPKS submits to the Sabang Zone Council (DKS) chaired by the Aceh Gebernur. This is in accordance with the Aceh Gebernur Decree Number 510/289/2009 which states that the BPKS is an element of the Implementation of the Sabang Zone Council in the field of management and development of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Area. According to Article 21 of the decision it was stated that in carrying out the management and development of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Area. Employee involvement in decision making and the provision of a work environment at Sabang BPKS has been carried out, but the reality shows low. Indicators of low job satisfaction can be seen from work morale, feeling bored in completing predetermined work and other indicators. Some of the employees in the institution even wanted to move to other institutions which they considered better. Even though the low level of job satisfaction with the indicators described above is only felt by a handful of employees, it can at least signal that some BPKS employees have problems in their job satisfaction.

When associated with achievement motivation that exists in each employee is different between one employee and another employee. This can be clearly seen from their willingness to accept assignments, a sense of responsibility for the work that is charged, and a willingness to face the risk of "failure" in carrying out their duties. Even though the achievement motivation in each employee is inseparable from the desire to fulfill job satisfaction, because basically every employee is motivated to carry out the task in the hope of being able to fulfill his needs / satisfaction. The problem in this study is how the influence of involvement in decision-making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation towards job satisfaction of the Employee Agency of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Zone of Aceh Province. Whereas, the purpose of the study was to determine the

effect of involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation on employee job satisfaction Agency for Exploitation of Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Area of Aceh Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an important thing that everyone has in working with. With a high level of job satisfaction, they will work with the utmost care that the goals of the organization can achieve well. Job satisfaction is a positive emotional state from evaluating one's work experience. [3] Job satisfaction is also a dynamic trait, in the sense that satisfaction is not a fixed condition because it can change by forces both inside and outside the work environment. Luthans, as cited by, [4] suggests job satisfaction is pleasurable or emotional state positive results from the tea appraisal of one's job experience. Job satisfaction is the difference between how much something should be received and how much something he actually receives. [5] Job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state in which employees view their work. [6] Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is fun and loves work. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction can be enjoyed at work, outside employment, and a combination of in and out work. Satisfaction in work is job satisfaction enjoyed in work by gaining work praise, placement, treatment, equipment, and a good working environment. Employees who prefer to enjoy work satisfaction in work will prioritize their work rather than repay the service even though the service is important.

Job Satisfaction Theories

There are several theories related to job satisfaction. The well-known theory of job satisfaction is: [7]

1. Theory of discrepancy theory. This theory measures one's job satisfaction by

calculating the difference between something that is supposed to be and the reality that is felt. So that if the power is obtained more than desired, then people will be even more satisfied, so there is a discrepancy, but it is a positive discrepancy. A person's job satisfaction depends on the difference between something that is considered to be obtained with what is achieved.

2. Equity theory. This theory suggests that people will feel satisfied or dissatisfied, depending on whether there is equity in a situation, especially a work situation. According to this theory, the main components in the theory of justice are input, outcome, injustice. Input is a valuable factor for employees who are considered to support their work, such as education, experience, skills, and the number of tasks and equipment or equipment used to carry out their work. Results are something that is considered valuable by an employee obtained from his jobs, such as wages/salaries, side benefits, symbols, status, rewards, and opportunities for success or self-actualization. According to this theory, each employee will compare the ratio of input to his results with the ratio of input to the results of others. If the comparison is considered fair enough, then the employee will feel satisfied. If the comparison is not balanced but profitable, it can lead to satisfaction, but it may not. But if the comparison is not balanced there will be dissatisfaction. [7]

Theory of two factors (Two-factor theory). According to this theory, job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are different things. Satisfaction and dissatisfaction with the job is not a continuous variable. That is, satisfaction and job dissatisfaction do not last all the time. Sometimes employees feel satisfaction in working, on the contrary, sometimes employees feel dissatisfied at work. This theory formulates job characteristics into two groups, namely satisfying or motivating and dissatisfying. Satisfaction is the factors or situations

needed as a source of job satisfaction which consists of work that is interesting, full of challenges, opportunities for achievement, opportunities to get awards and promotions. The influence of these factors will lead to satisfaction, but not fulfilling these factors will lead to dissatisfaction, but not fulfilling this factor does not always lead to dissatisfaction. Dissatisfied (hygiene factors) are factors that are a source of dissatisfaction, which consists of salary/wages, supervision, interpersonal relationships, working conditions, and status. This factor is needed to meet the biological urge and basic needs of employees. If this factor is not met, employees will not be satisfied. However, if the size of this factor is sufficient to meet these needs, the employees will not be disappointed even though they have not been satisfied.

Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction

There are five prominent work satisfaction models that will classify the causes. Causes are the fulfillment of needs, incompatibility, achievement of values, equations and character / genetic components. ^[8]

1. Fulfillment of Needs
2. Mismatch.
3. Achieve Value
4. Equations
5. Genetic Character / Component

There are five indicators that can affect job satisfaction, namely:

1. Payments, such as payments and wages
2. The work itself
3. Co-workers
4. Job promotion
5. Supervisor (supervision). ^[9]

The factors that increase employee job satisfaction in improving performance are as follows: ^[10]

1. Psychological factors are factors related to psychology, which are related to interest, peace in work, attitude to work, talent, and skills:
2. Social factors are factors associated with social interaction, fellow employees,

with their employers, all employees of various types of work:

3. Physical factors are factors related to the physical condition of the work environment and physical conditions of employees, including the type of work, arrangement of rest periods, work equipment, room conditions, lighting temperature, air transportation, employee health conditions, age, etc.:
4. Financial factors are factors related to the guarantee and health of employees who complete the system and guarantee of payment, Social Security, various types of benefits, facilities provided, promotions and so on.

Overall, the factors that can affect job satisfaction, such as leadership style, work productivity, motivation, the locus of control, fulfillment of expectations Thus, employee job satisfaction is the result of various interrelated factors. ^[7] The factors used to measure employee satisfaction are: ^[7]

1. Contents of work, the appearance of actual work assignments and job control:
2. Supervision:
3. Organization and management:
4. Opportunities to progress:
5. Salary and other financial benefits
6. Co-workers:
7. Working conditions. ^[7]

Job Satisfaction Measurement

Job satisfaction is about people who experience work and its aspects. There are several reasons companies must really pay attention to job satisfaction, which can be categorized according to the focus of employees or companies. The measurement of work results can be illustrated in the following figure: ^[7]

Figure 1. Motivation Performance Model As Measurement of Job Satisfaction

From figure 1 above, the probability of successful implementation is seen by someone in various ways. As an actor, the employees will assess their abilities, both knowledge, and skills, to introduce whether they will be able to finish the job properly or not, so they can get the desired reward. How to support from his superiors so that he can succeed, and the extent of cooperation with his colleagues will help his success. Or the extent to which he can obtain the necessary skills for how long it takes to carry out the work if the value of the benefits to be obtained and the probability of successful work appear positive. These employees generally decide to carry out activities to achieve the desired benefits.

Organizations can do better in achieving goals, if more attention is given to humans in organizations, such as in decision making. [11] A similar opinion was also expressed by [12] which states that "the individual is always the basic strategic factor in the organization, there must be encouraged to cooperate and to contribute to his effort to the organization". By involving members of the organization in decision making, and the more people involved in decision making, the more effective decisions will be made. [13] Because they will be complete, and will carry out the decisions that have been taken carefully, and loyal to the organization in order to achieve goals. [14]

Assessment of the Work Environment

Between the work environment and job satisfaction, there is a positive relationship, and the work environment influences the work productivity of an organization. [15] The formation of a work environment that is related to human capabilities and work productivity is influenced by physical, chemical, biological, physiological, metal and socio-economic factors. [16] Broadly speaking, the work environment is influenced by the following factors. First, work facilities, work environments that do not support the implementation of work contribute to poor performance, such as lack of work tools, stuffy workspace, poor ventilation, and unclear procedures. [17] Second, salaries and benefits. Salaries that are not in line with the expectations of the workers will make workers glance at the work environment at any time which guarantees the achievement of workers' expectations. [18] Third, work relations. Working groups with high cohesiveness and loyalty will increase work productivity, because between one worker and another worker will support each other the achievement of goals and/or results. [17] Genetically, each individual has the ability to adapt to the environment certain behavioral patterns to overcome environmental problems. However, the formation of a work environment that supports work productivity will lead to job satisfaction for workers in all organizations. [19]

Definition of Achievement Motivation and Motivation

The etymology of motivation comes from the word "move" in Latin which means to move. Motivating (to motivate) means the action of someone who wants to influence others to behave in certain cases. Moekijat in the management dictionary cited by [20] says that motivation is 1). Every feeling or desire that greatly influences the willingness of people, so that people are encouraged to act: 2) The influence of forces that cause behavior: 3) Processes

determine the behavior or behavior of individuals to goals.

Limiting that "motivation is the power of encouragement that results in an organization member willing and willing to direct the will in the form of expertise or skills of energy and the time to organize various activities that want to be his responsibility will fulfill obligations, in the level of achievement of goals and various goals of the organization predetermined. ^[21]

The theory of achievement motivation was put forward by McClelland who argued that the need for achievement is a function of driving ability, effort, and desire to achieve goals. This theory argues that employees have potential energy reserves. How this energy is released and used depends on the strength of the motivation of a person and the situation and opportunities available. This energy will be utilized by employees because it is driven by a lack of basic motives and needs involved, success expectations and incentive values that are attached to the goal. McClelland groups three human needs that can motivate work passion, namely (1) the need for achievement (2) the need for affiliation and (3) the need for strength. ^[22] Achievement motivation is the result of business interaction, satisfaction, and reward for achieving goals. ^[23, 24]

Characteristics of Achievement Motivation

The need for achievement as a desire to carry out a task or a difficult job. People who are motivated to excel, have three general characteristics; First preference for doing tasks with moderate difficulty. Both high achievers also like situations where their performance arises because of their own efforts and not other factors, such as luck. Third, classifying employees who have high achievement motivation is that they want more feedback about their successes and failures. ^[25,26] There are three general characteristics of people who have high achievement motivation, namely (1) the ability to set personal goals that are high

but rationally achievable, (2) more committed to the satisfaction of personal achievement rather than external lure and (3) desire feedback from his work. ^[27,2]

Engagement Involvement in Achieving Decision Making and Motivation with Job Satisfaction

Employee involvement in decision making can lead to satisfaction at work. This is due to the involvement in decision making, an employee will feel valued in work. ^[28] In addition, employees who are involved in decision making will feel that the work carried out is part of the decision itself. Especially in matters relating to the technique of carrying out work. If employees are involved in determining the procedures for carrying out their work they will be able to provide suggestions on how to do the work in the best way according to them. While work is one of the factors that can affect work satisfaction. ^[29]

Furthermore, achievement motivation is the desire to achieve success at work. Employees who are motivated at work have methods for carrying out tasks with moderate difficulty, and like situations where their performance arises because of their own efforts and not because of other factors. In this regard ^[30] states, achievement motivation is the result of business interactions, satisfaction, and rewards for achieving goals. In an organization, people will always be motivated to move to achieve a goal if they feel it is part of their personal goals. The weak strength of achievement motivation depends on the extent of hope that is to be achieved, the strength of the basis that gives rise to motivation depends on the amount of satisfaction desired. The special characteristics of people who have high achievement needs are happy to assume responsibility and are confident in their abilities. ^[2] From the description that it is clear that involvement in decision making and achievement motivation has an influence on the working papacy of an employee.

Research Hypothesis

From the research background, the purpose of the literature and the results of previous research, the ones who become hypnotic in this study are involved in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation have a positive effect on employee job satisfaction Office of the Executing Agency of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Zone (BPKS) of the Province of Aceh.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Location and Object of Research

This research was conducted at the Executing Agency of Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Zone (BPKS) in Sabang, Aceh Province. The object of the study relates to the job satisfaction of the agency's employees who are associated with involvement in decision making, research on the work environment and achievement motivation possessed by the employee.

Population and Samples

The study population was all of the 126 employees of the Office of the Agency for the Execution of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Zone (BPKS) of Aceh Province. For the purposes of this study, a sample will be drawn. Determination of the number of samples is sought using the Slovin formula as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$$

Information:

e = Percentage of accuracy due to errors in sampling

N = Population Size / Sample Size

With a sampling allowance level of 10%, the number of study samples is 56 employees, sought by calculation as follows:

$$n = \frac{126}{1+126(0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{126}{1+126(0,01)}$$

$$n = \frac{126}{1+1,26} = 55,75 \text{ rounded up to } 56 \text{ people.}$$

Taking a number of samples above, carried out conveniently sampling. This method of sampling can facilitate researchers in determining an employee who is used as a research sample. However, sampling still prioritizes employees who have higher access to everything related to decision making on BPKS such as deputies, each head of the field of employee participants below who are considered to have better access to technical decisions.

Operational Variables

The research variables consisted of job satisfaction as a dependent variable, with involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation as independent variables.

Analysis Tools

Data analysis equipment used to be able to explain the research problems as formulated are multiple linear regression. Metamorphically formulated as follows: ^[31]

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

Where:

Y = Job Satisfaction

a = Constant

X1 = Planning in Decision Making

X2 = Assessment of the Work Environment

X3 = Achievement Motivation

b1, b2, and b3 = regression coefficients X1, X2 and X3

e = Error term

To find out the closeness of the relationship between the independent variables (involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation) with employee job satisfaction as the dependent variable the correlation coefficient (R) is used. Furthermore, to find out the magnitude of

performance variations can be explained by the three independent variables used the terminated coefficient (R^2).

Hypothesis testing

At the 95 percent assembly level, the hypothesis in this study can be described as follows:

Ho: involvement in decision making, research on the work environment and achievement motivation did not significantly influence the Job Satisfaction of Employees of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Port Free Trade Zone Office.

Ha: involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation did not have a significant positive effect on the job satisfaction of employees of the Sabang Free Port and Free Trade Zone Free Trade Office (BPKS) office.

Hypothesis testing uses statistical F-Test and t-test equipment. The F test is used to determine the effect of the three independent variables simultaneously on employee job satisfaction, with the following conditions.

1. If the value of F count > from the value of F table, then the hypothesis (Ha) is accepted.
2. If the F value is calculated < from the value of F table, then the hypothesis (Ha) is rejected.

Furthermore, the provisions of hypothesis testing using the t-test are as follows:

1. If the value of t counts an independent variable > t value of the table can be interpreted that the relevant independent variables have a significant effect on employee work capacity.
2. If the value of t counts an independent variable < t value of the table can be interpreted that the related independent variables have a significant effect on employee workload

Testing for Reliability and Validity

Reliability Testing

Reliability of measurement shows how far the measurement is not biased (error-free free) and therefore guarantees consistent measurements across time and

cross-religious items in the instrument. In other words, the reliability of a measurement is an indication of stability and consistency where the instrument measures the concept and helps assess the "accuracy" of measurement. [32] In this study, reject the size of the reliability of a questionnaire is the Cronbach alpha indigo obtained through statistical calculations. The acceptable Cronbach alpha value was 0.70. [33] This means that a questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach alpha value obtained is above 0.70.

Validity Testing

A measurement scale is called valid if he does what is supposed to be done and measures what should be measured. If the measurement scale is invalid, then it is not useful for researchers because it does not measure what should be done. [34] In this study, determining validity can be done by looking for the correlation value of the scores of each item with the total item score for each variable. Then the calculated r value obtained from the correlation is compared with the r table value at the 95 percent confidence level. If the value of r count > r table item statement is declared valid. Conversely if the value of r count < r table, then the item statement is invalid. [35]

Heteroscedasticity testing

Heteroscedasticity is a variation of data used to create a model that is not constant or that shows the greater variation along with the enlargement of X and Y values. Heteroscedasticity occurs when the variance is not constant, so as if there are several groups of data that have different error quantities. A good regression model is one that does not occur heteroscedasticity or heteroscedasticity. Detecting the presence or absence of physicality can be done by looking at the presence or absence of certain patterns on the scatterplot graph. Heteroscedasticity will be detected if the plot shows a systematic pattern. [36,37,38]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity test

Validity test is used to measure the validity of the data obtained. A measurement scale is called valid if he does what is supposed to be done and measures what should be measured. If the measurement scale is not valid, then it is not useful for researchers because it does not measure what should be done. In this study, the determination of validity can be done by finding the correlation value of the scores of each item with the total item score for each variable. Then the calculated value obtained from the correlation is compared with the r table value at the 95 percent confidence level provided that if the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$ item statement is declared valid. Conversely, if the value of $r_{count} < r_{table}$ mak the item statement is invalid.

The job satisfaction variable consisting of 8 (eight) statement items is represented by item codes A1, A2, A3 to A8. The value of r count for the first statement (A1) shows a number of 0.693. This number is greater than the r table ($n =$

56) of 0.266. Thus it can be interpreted that all items of the first statement relating to job satisfaction are declared valid. Furthermore, the calculated value for the second statement item (A2) to the eighth statement item (A8) is also greater than the r table value, so that all statement items related to the variable job satisfaction are also declared valid.

Furthermore, the variable involvement in decision making consists of 6 (six) statement items denoted by B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, and B6. The value of r calculated for the first statement item (B1) shows a number of 0.653. This is greater than the value of r count for the second statement item (B2) until the sixth statement item (B6) also shows the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$. Thus it can be interpreted as all statements related to the variable involvement in decision making declared valid. For more details about the results of testing, validity can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Validity test results

No	Variable	Item Code	R-Value Calculate	Value of R Table (n = 56)	Information
1	Job satisfaction	A1	0,693	0,266	Valid
		A2	0,664	0,266	Valid
		A3	0,605	0,266	Valid
		A4	0,661	0,266	Valid
		A5	0,679	0,266	Valid
		A6	0,467	0,266	Valid
		A7	0,498	0,266	Valid
		A8	0,509	0,266	Valid
2	Engagement in Decision Making	B1	0,653	0,266	Valid
		B2	0,730	0,266	Valid
		B3	0,619	0,266	Valid
		B4	0,626	0,266	Valid
		B5	0,681	0,266	Valid
		B6	0,737	0,266	Valid
3	Assessment of the Work Environment	C1	0,784	0,266	Valid
		C2	0,713	0,266	Valid
		C3	0,707	0,266	Valid
		C4	0,575	0,266	Valid
		C5	0,714	0,266	Valid
		C6	0,699	0,266	Valid
4	Achievement motivation	D1	0,608	0,266	Valid
		D2	0,545	0,266	Valid
		D3	0,547	0,266	Valid
		D4	0,552	0,266	Valid
		D5	0,632	0,266	Valid
		D6	0,562	0,266	Valid
		D7	0,845	0,266	Valid
		D8	0,641	0,266	Valid

Source: Primary data (processed) 2019.

Based on Table 1 above it can be seen that the value of the calculated correlation (r_{count}) for each item statement contained in the assessment variable in the

work environment (with code C1-C6), is greater than the number of r table. So is the case with statement items contained in achievement motivation variables (with

code D1-D8). Thus it can be interpreted that all statement items relating to the assessment variables in the work environment and achievement motivation are also declared valid. Based on the description above, it is clear that all statement items contained in each research variable are job satisfaction, involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation are declared valid, meaning the questionnaire used for data collection can be used to measure what should be-being measured.

Reliability Test Results

Reliability (reliability) a measurement shows the extent of the measurement without bias (error-free - error free) and therefore guarantees consistent measurements across time and cross-religious items in the instructor. In this study, the benchmark for the reliability of a questionnaire is the Cronbach alpha value obtained through statistical analysis. A questionnaire is declared reliable if the calculation results show indigo Cronbach

alpha above 0.70. Conversely, if the Cronbach alpha value is below 0.70. Then the questionnaire was declared not reliable. The results of the statistical calculations show the Cronbach alpha value for the variable job satisfaction variable of 0.736. This number is greater than 0.70. It can be interpreted that the questionnaire used in data collection related to job satisfaction was declared reliable. Furthermore, the Cronbach alpha value for the variable involvement in decision making shows a number of 0.782 which is also greater than 0.70. So that it can be interpreted that the questionnaire used in data collection related to involvement in decision making was also declared reliable. Nilia Cronbach alpha for the next two variables shows a number of 0.787 for the assessment variable in the work environment and of 0.772 for the variable achievement motivation. Thus it can be interpreted that the questionnaire used to collect data relating to the assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation was also stated to be reliable as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Reliability test results

No	Variable	Item Amount	Cronbach alpha value	Information
1	Job satisfaction	8	0,736	Reliable
2	Engagement in Decision Making	6	0,782	Reliable
3	Assessment of the Work Environment	6	0,787	Reliable
4	Achievement motivation	8	0,772	Reliable

Source: Primary data (processed), 2019.

Based on table 2 above, it can be seen that the Cronbach alpha value in each study variant is greater than 0.70 because of the value needed to test the reliability of the questionnaire. Thus it can be interpreted that the questionnaire used for research data collection has met the reliability requirements. With word lines, the questionnaire used to collect data relating to the variables under study was assessed to indicate the accuracy, accuracy, or consistency of the tools in expressing symptoms related to the related variables.

Multicollinearity Test Results

Symptoms of multicollinearity indicate the occurrence of a significant relationship between fellow independent variables. Multiple linear regression

requires no symptoms. This is because, if the symptoms of multicollinearity occur, then the change of one independent variable does not only have an impact on the change in the dependent variable but can also result in changes in other independent variables, so the influence of each independent variable is difficult to ascertain. To find out the presence or absence of symptoms of multicollinearity is seen from the value of the variance inflation factor (VIF), with the provision that the VIF value is > 5.00. Can be interpreted as a symptom of multicollinearity. Conversely, if VIF value < 5.00 means that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity. The results of testing the VIF value of each independent variable showed a number of 2.763 for the variables

of involvement in decision making, amounting to 3.888 for the assessment variables in the work environment and at 2.955 for the achievement motivation variables as shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3. VIF Values of Each Test Result Variable Multicollinearity

No	Variable	VIF value
1	Engagement in Decision Making	2,763
2	Assessment of the work environment	3,888
3	Achievement motivation	2,955

Table 3 above shows the VIF value of each independent variable is smaller than 5.00 so that it can be interpreted that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity, with other times there is no strong relationship between the independent variables.

Description of Variable Job Satisfaction

In accordance with the questionnaire used in the data explorer, the variable job satisfaction consists of 8 (eight) items of positive questions. Indicators used include feelings of pride and success that employees have, a sense of responsibility for work, a feeling of belonging and being part of the institution. Employee satisfaction can be measured based on the choice of answers in the form of the level of agreement given by employees in each statement can be interpreted in general respondents tend to agree that they have a sense of responsibility in carrying out the tasks charged. For more details about the frequency distribution of respondents based on the level of agreement with statements relating to job satisfaction.

Description of Variable Engagement in Decision Making

Variables of involvement in decision making are also described in the form of positive statements. The indicator used consists of the willingness of the leadership to involve employees in decision making, willingness to take part in the decision making, the ability of employees to express opinions, provide criticism to the opinions

of others, willingness to implement decisions and independence of employees in carrying out decisions. The high intensity of employee involvement in decision-making at the Office of the Concession Board of the Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone (BPKS) of the Province of Aceh was measured based on the level of an agreement they gave in each statement. The results of data processing showed that each of the 26 people and 19 respondents agreed and strongly agreed that the leadership or supervisor involved them and other employees in the meeting (meeting).

Description of Assessment Variables in the Work Environment

Assessment of the work environment is basically an assessment of employees of factors outside of humans both physical and non-physical in an environment in which they work. Indicators used in measuring work environment variables consist of capabilities (number) of facilities used by employees in carrying out work, quality of facilities, suitability of salaries, opportunity to obtain additional income, interaction with superiors / fellow work colleagues and smooth communication. Each of these indicators is described in the form of positive statements. The poor assessment of employees on the work environment for the Sabang Free and Free Trade Zone Free Trade Agency (BPKS) Office is based on the alternative level of approval they gave in each statement. The results of the data collection indicate that each of the 35 people and 13 respondents agreed and fearfully agreed that in their work they were equipped with sufficient work facilities. For more details about the frequency distribution of respondents based on the level of agreement on statements relating to the assessment of the work environment, see Table 4 below:

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Level of Approval of Related Statements with Assessment of the Work Environment

No	Statement	Frequency					Average
		Disagree	Less agree	Doubtful	Agree	Strongly agree	
1	In your work, you are equipped with sufficient work facilities.	-	3	5	35	13	4,040
2	The quality of work facilities/equipment used is quite good so that it can support the smooth implementation of tasks.	-	5	13	25	13	3,820
3	The salary you earn is in accordance with the sacrifice you have given.	-	8	12	32	4	3,570
4	You receive other income besides salaries, such as benefits and other bonuses.	-	2	10	36	8	3,890
5	There is an interaction between you and your boss or fellow colleagues in carrying out your work.	-	5	16	21	14	3,790
6	Communication between you and your boss or fellow co-workers runs smoothly.	1	6	12	26	11	3,710
Average							3,804

Source: Primary data (processed), 2019.

Table 4 above shows the average score of the approval level of 3.804 this figure is close to 4.00 (the score for answer choices agree) can be interpreted generally employees of the Office of the Free Trade and Free Trade Zone of Sabang Free Zone (BPKS) who are research respondents tend to choose alternative choice answers agree to all statement items relating to the assessment of the work environment. Even if there are officials who choose alternative choices, the less agree is only a small part of the total number of respondents.

Description of Achievement Motivation Variables

Stated motivation can be interpreted as a strong desire to achieve success in work

that is characterized by self-actualization efforts, according to excellence and the implementation of optimal tasks based on rational. Along with the questionnaire used in data collection, the variable achievement motivation was described in 8 (eight) items of positive statements. It can be interpreted generally that employees of the Sabang Free and Pelabahan Free Trade Zone Offices (BPKS) tend to agree that they always want to be competent / compete in completing their work with their fellow co-workers. Table 5 shows the frequency distribution of respondents based on the level of objectives of the statements relating to achievement motivation.

Table 5. Respondents' Frequency Distribution Based on Level of Approval of Related Statements with Achievement Motivation.

No	Statement	Frequency					Average
		Disagree	Less agree	Doubtful	Agree	Strongly agree	
1	You can and always try to make the target/implementation of the work that is rational.	-	4	8	25	19	4,050
2	You are sure that you are able to be the best at completing work.	-	3	8	33	12	3,960
3	You always want to compete in working with fellow workers.	-	6	13	25	12	3,770
4	You have pride in the success of carrying out work.	1	15	20	15	5	3,140
5	You always receive every task that is assigned to you.	-	2	11	26	17	4,040
6	You are always responsible for carrying out tasks that are charged.	-	-	9	36	11	4,040
7	You often do evaluations or feedback from your work that you do.	1	2	16	23	14	3,840
8	You are willing to face risks related to the responsibilities that are charged to you.	1	9	22	18	6	3,340
Average							3,772

Source: Primary data (processed), 2019.

Table 5 above shows the average score of the approval level of 3.772 this figure is close to 4.00 (the score for the

choice of answers agrees) can be interpreted in general the employees of the Office of the Free Trade and Free Trade Zone of Sabang

Free Zone (BPKS) of Aceh Province who researched respondents tend to choose alternative to agree on answers to all statement items relating to achievement motivation. Even if there are those who choose the alternative answer option, they agree that only a small percentage of the total respondents.

DISCUSSION

Overall, satisfaction in employee work is in accordance with employment decisions. Assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation that is in the employee. The higher the level of participation in making decisions and the higher the level of work and the higher the achievement, the higher job satisfaction will be. If there is someone who can argue, they

must be involved in the decision-making process, and do not have problems with the work environment and have low achievement motivation. Because it is in line with the research topic, the work satisfaction of employees of the Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone Offices Agency (BPKS) is made from meetings in decision making, improving the work environment and trying to achieve. Data processing results from the results of decision-making, assessment of the work environment and positive achievement motivation on job satisfaction of the Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone Offices Office (BPKS). This is considered by the positive value of the regression coefficients of each variable as seen in the following SPSS output section.

Table 6. The Output Spss Section that Shows the Regression Coefficient of Each Independent Variable

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std.error	beta			tolerance	VIF
1 (constant)	1.047	.235		4.447	.000		
Engagement in decision making,	218	.090	.278	2.423	.019	.362	2.763
Assessment of the work environment,	266	.105	.346	2.538	.014	.257	3.888
Achievement motivation	278	.104	.318	2.681	.010	.338	2.995

Based on the SPSS output section above, then making the proposed assessment of job satisfaction as involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation is formulated in the equation below:

$$Y = 1,047 + 0,218X_1 + 0,266x^2 + 0,278X_3$$

The constant value of 1.047 can be interpreted statistically if the value of X_1 , X_2 , and X_3 approaches 0 (zero) then the value of y will approach 1.047. When associated with using a Likert scale (interval Likert) with intervals of 1-5, then the value of Y approaching 1.047 means that employee job satisfaction is classified as very low, while the values of X_1 , X_2 , and X_3 close to zero can mean that employees have a poor assessment of their involvement in decision making, they also have a poor assessment of the work environment, and they also have very low achievement motivation. Thus associated with the focus

of this study's study, the Y value of 1.047 can be interpreted that if employees have a bad assessment of involvement in decision making (employees are not involved in decision making) and have a poor assessment of the work environment is not good, and have low achievement motivation. Then the work satisfaction of the employees concerned will also be very low.

The regression equation above shows that the regression coefficient value X_1 (for the variables of involvement in decision making) shows a number of 0.218 statistically it can be interpreted that any increase in variable scores involving 1.00 decision making in the Likert scale unit will be able to increase the average value Job satisfaction score of 0.218. This means that the higher the involvement of an employee in decision making will the higher the job satisfaction of the employee. Conversely, the lower the involvement of employees in

decision making, job satisfaction will also be increasingly low.

Regression coefficient X_2 (for assessment variables in the work environment) shows a number of 0.266. This number can be interpreted as each increase in the average value of the score of the variable assessment in the work environment of 1.00 (in the Likert scale unit) will increase the job satisfaction score by 0.266. Thus it can be understood that the assessment of the work environment also has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction. The better the employee's judgment. Conversely, employees with relatively poor judgment on the work environment will tend to have relatively low job satisfaction.

The interest between achievement motivation and job satisfaction also shows the same tendency, where the higher the achievement motivation possessed by an employee, the higher job satisfaction of the employee. This is indicated by the regression coefficient X_3 (for achievement motivation variables of 0.278. Based on the regression coefficients of the three independent variables described above it can be seen that the variable that has the

most dominant influence on job satisfaction is achievement motivation. This is due to the regression coefficient for this variable 0.278 is greater than the value of the regression coefficients of the other two variables, then following the assessment variable in the work environment is ranked second with a regression coefficient of 0.266 otherwise the variable involvement in decision making is in third place which means that of the three independent variables, involvement in decision making has the smallest influence when compared with the assessment variables in the work environment and achievement motivation.

To find out the closeness of the relationship between employee job satisfaction and involvement in decision making, an assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation used the correlation coefficient (R). On the other hand, to find out the magnitude of the variation in job satisfaction which can be explained by the three independent variables, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is used for the SPSS output which shows each of these coefficient values as follows.

Table 7. Sections of Output Spss that Shows the Value of the Correlation Coefficient (R) and Determination Coefficient Value (R^2)
Model summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of The estimate	Durbin – watson
1	.867 ^a	.752	.738	.23222	1.710

- a. Predictor: (constant), achievement motivation, involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment.
b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction.

Based on the SPSS output section above, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.867. This number is in the interval of 0.80-1.00 which means that the relationship between employee job satisfaction and involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation is very tight, then the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.752 can be interpreted as 75, 2 percent of employee job satisfaction can be explained by involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement

motivation, by 24.8 percent again (1-0,752) explained by other factors besides the three variables.

Proof of Hypothesis

The testing of the hypothesis described earlier uses F Test statistics and t-test. F Test statistics are basically used to determine the significance of the influence of independent variables (involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation) simultaneously on employee job satisfaction. While t-test statistics are used

to determine the significance (real or not in fact) of the influence of each of these variables (partially) on employee job satisfaction.

The results of testing the F test statistics show the calculated F value of 52,599. While the value of F table at 95% confidence level shows a number of 2.786. Because the value of F count > F table (52,599 > 2,786) then the Ha hypothesis is accepted which means involvement in decision making, assessment of work environment and achievement motivation has a significant effect on the working capacity of Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone Offices (BPKS).

The results of testing the t-test statistic show the value of t count of 2.423

for the value of involvement in decision making, amounting to 2.538 for the assessment variable in the work environment and at 2.681 for the achievement motivation variable. The value of t table at 95% confidence level shows a number of 2.005. Because the value of t count for each variable greater than the value of t table can be interpreted partially in the involvement in decision making, the assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction. For more details about the F test and t-test as a benchmark for testing hypotheses, you can see the following table.

Table 8. Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Form of Testing	Statistical value		Information
	F count	F table	
Simultaneous testing	52,599	2,786	The three variables have a significant effect (Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected)
Partial testing	T count	T table	
Involvement in decision making	2,423	2,005	Engagement in decision making is significant.
Assessment of the work environment	2,538	2,005	Assessment of the work environment has a significant effect.
Achievement motivation	2,681	2,005	Achievement motivation has a significant effect.

Source: Primary data (processed), 2019.

Based on table 8, it is clear that both in simultaneous and joint sampling. Involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and performance motivation have a significant effect on the work satisfaction of employees of the Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone Office of the Free Trade Offices (BPKS). Positive influence is seen from the regression coefficient value of each variable which shows a positive number, and the significance of the influence is indicated by the value of F count > F table, and the value of t count each variable > t table.

Based on the explanation above, it is clear that an increase in the intensity of employee involvement in decision making, an increase in the assessment of the work environment and an increase in achievement motivation can significantly increase the job satisfaction of Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone Offices employees (BPKS).

CONCLUSION

The conclusions obtained after conducting this research are:

1. Involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation positively influence the job satisfaction of employees of the Sabang Free Trade and Free Trade Zone Office of the Concession Agency, indicated by the regard equation $Y = 1.047 + 0.218X_1 + 0.266X_2 + 0.278X_3$. The variable with the greatest influence on employee employment is achievement motivation (X3) with a coefficient of 0.278. Then following the assessment of the work environment (X2) in the second position with a regression coefficient of 0.266.
2. The relationship between job satisfaction and involvement in decision making, assessment of the work

environment and achievement motivation are very tight, indicated by the correlation coefficient (R) of 0.867. Furthermore, 75.20 percent of employee job satisfaction is influenced by involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation. The remaining 24.80 percent (1-0,752) is influenced by other factors besides these three factors.

3. Statistical test results show the value of $F_{count} > F_{table}$ and value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$, can be interpreted both simultaneously and deliberately involvement in decision making, assessment of the work environment and achievement motivation have a significant effect on employee job satisfaction Free and Pelabuhan Free from Sabang. Thus the hypothesis H_a is accepted and conversely the hypothesis H_o is rejected.

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